

On New Types of Weakly Neutrosophic Crisp Closed Functions

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Abstract. This study utilizes some ideas of α -closed and semi- α -closed sets in neutrosophic crisp topological space to state roughly innovative categories of weakly neutrosophic crisp closed functions such as; neutrosophic crisp α^* -closed functions, neutrosophic crisp α^{**} -closed functions, neutrosophic crisp semi- α -closed functions, neutrosophic crisp semi- α^* -closed and neutrosophic crisp semi- α^{**} -closed functions. Moreover, the interactions among these kinds of feebly neutrosophic crisp closed functions and the suggestions for crisp closed functions are described. Furthermore, some theorems, properties, and remarks are debated.

Keywords: Neutrosophic crisp α^* -closed, neutrosophic crisp α^{**} -closed, neutrosophic crisp semi- α -closed, neutrosophic crisp semi- α^* -closed and neutrosophic crisp semi- α^{**} -closed functions.

1. Introduction

Smarandache [1,2] extended the view of sets by defending neutrosophic sets as a generality of Zadeh's fuzzy set concept, which states there is no accurate meaning for the set [3]. Soon after, the intuitionistic fuzzy set theory was submitted by Atanassov, such that he suggested that some elements have the degree of non-membership in the set [4]. The recently exhibited notions fascinated numerous scholars of conventional mathematics. Perhaps, fuzzy topology was set up by Chang [5] and Lowen [6] by redirecting the constructs from fuzzy sets to the traditional topological spaces. Additionally, the extraction of neutrosophic crisp topological space (shortly, NCTS) was announced by A. A. Salama et al. [7]. M. Abdel-Basset et al. [8-13] provided a new neutrosophic technique. The interpretation of neutrosophic crisp semi- α -closed sets was tendered by R. K. Al-Hamido et al. [14]. Some views of α gs continuity and α gs irresolute functions was examined by V. Banupriya et al. [15]. Some principles of neutrosophic α^m -continuity was demonstrated by R. Dhavaseelan et al. [16]. The gb-closed sets then gb-continuity was directed by C. Maheswari et al. [17]. The homeomorphism in neutrosophic topological spaces was generalized by M. H. PAGE et al. [18]. A weakly neutrosophic crisp continuity was established by Q. H. Imran et al. [19,20]. Recently, new types of open mappings in weakly neutrosophic crisp topology was defined by Al-Obaidi et al. [21].

The target of the study is to submit different categories of neutrosophic crisp closed functions in weakly forms, such as; neutrosophic crisp α^* -closed, neutrosophic crisp α^{**} -closed, neutrosophic crisp semi- α -closed, neutrosophic crisp semi- α^* -closed and neutrosophic crisp semi- α^{**} -closed functions. Additionally, the connections concerning these kinds of weakly neutrosophic crisp closed functions are illuminated, corresponding to the thoughts of neutrosophic crisp closed functions. As Well, some theorems, properties and remarks are demonstrated.

2. Preliminaries

Through this paper, $(\mathcal{J}, \zeta)$, $(\mathcal{J}, \eta)$ and $(\mathcal{K}, \gamma)$ (or in short $\mathcal{J}, \mathcal{J}$ and $\mathcal{K}$) constantly imply NCTSs. Assume that $\mathcal{L}$ be a neutrosophic crisp set in a NCTS $\mathcal{J}$, then

- $\mathcal{L}^c = \mathcal{J} - \mathcal{L}$ signifies the neutrosophic crisp complement of $\mathcal{L}$.
- $NC-cl(\mathcal{L})$ refers to the neutrosophic crisp closure of $\mathcal{L}$.
- $NC-int(\mathcal{L})$ speaks of the neutrosophic crisp interior of $\mathcal{L}$.

Definition 2.1 [7]: Assume non-empty fixed set $\mathcal{L}$ is sample space. The object with form $\mathcal{N} = \langle \mathcal{N}_1, \mathcal{N}_2, \mathcal{N}_3 \rangle$ is called a neutrosophic crisp set, for short NC-set such that $\mathcal{N}_1, \mathcal{N}_2$ and $\mathcal{N}_3$ are subsets of $\mathcal{L}$ with the mutually disjoint property.

Definition 2.2: Let $\mathcal{L}$ be a NC-subset of a NCTS $\mathcal{J}$, then we have the following

- i. $NC\alpha$ -CS is denoted as a neutrosophic crisp α -closed set [18] if $NC-cl(NC-int(NC-cl(\mathcal{L}))) \subseteq \mathcal{L}$.
- ii. $NC\alpha$ -OSs is signified as a neutrosophic crisp α -open set (the complement of a $NC\alpha$ -CS) in $\mathcal{J}$.
- iii. $NC\alpha C(\mathcal{J})$ (resp. $NC\alpha O(\mathcal{J})$) is represented as the collection of each $NC\alpha$ -CSs (resp. $NC\alpha$ -OSs) of $\mathcal{J}$.
- iv. $NCS\alpha$ -CS is indicated as a neutrosophic crisp semi- α -closed set [14] if

$$NC-int(NC-cl(NC-int(NC-cl(\mathcal{L})))) \subseteq \mathcal{L}$$

or regularly if there exists a $NC\alpha$ -CS $\mathcal{D}$ in $\mathcal{J}$ such that $NC-int(\mathcal{D}) \subseteq \mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{D}$.

- v. $NCS\alpha$ -OS is designated as a neutrosophic crisp semi- α -open set (the complement of a $NCS\alpha$ -CS) in $\mathcal{J}$.
- vi. $NCS\alpha C(\mathcal{J})$ (resp. $NCS\alpha O(\mathcal{J})$) is shown as the collection of each $NCS\alpha$ -CSs (resp. $NCS\alpha$ -OSs) of $\mathcal{J}$.

Remark 2.3 [14,20]: In a NCTS $\mathcal{J}$, the resulting declarations hang on, and the reverse of each declaration is a fallacy:

- i. Each NC-CS is a $NC\alpha$ -CS and $NCS\alpha$ -CS.
- ii. Each $NC\alpha$ -CS is a $NCS\alpha$ -CS.

Theorem 2.4 [18]: For any NC-subset $\mathcal{L}$ of a NCTS $\mathcal{J}$, $\mathcal{L} \in NC\alpha C(\mathcal{J})$ iff there exists a NC-CS $\mathcal{D}$ such that $NC-cl(NC-int(\mathcal{D})) \subseteq \mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{D}$.

Definition 2.5: A function $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ is called:

- i. Neutrosophic crisp closed (briefly NC-closed) [7] iff for each NC-CS $\mathcal{L}$ in $\mathcal{J}$, then $\psi(\mathcal{L})$ is a NC-CS in $\mathcal{J}$.
- ii. Neutrosophic crisp α -closed (briefly $NC\alpha$ -closed) [19] iff for each NC-CS $\mathcal{L}$ in $\mathcal{J}$, then $\psi(\mathcal{L})$ is a $NC\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{J}$.

Theorem 2.6 [7]:

- i. A function $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ is NC-closed iff $NC-cl(\psi(\mathcal{L})) \subseteq \psi(NC-cl(\mathcal{L}))$, for every $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{J}$.
- ii. A function $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ is neutrosophic crisp continuous (shortly NC-continuous) iff for each NC-CS $\mathcal{L}$ in $\mathcal{J}$, then $\psi^{-1}(\mathcal{L})$ is a NC-CS in $\mathcal{J}$.
- iii. A function $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ is NC-continuous iff $NC-int(\psi(\mathcal{L})) \subseteq \psi(NC-int(\mathcal{L}))$, for every $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{J}$.

3. Weakly Neutrosophic Crisp Closed Functions

Definition 3.1: Assume $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ is a function, then ψ is named as the following:

- i. Neutrosophic crisp α^* -closed (briefly $NC\alpha^*$ -closed) iff for each $NC\alpha$ -CS $\mathcal{L}$ in $\mathcal{J}$, then $\psi(\mathcal{L})$ is a $NC\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{J}$.

ii. Neutrosophic crisp α^{**} -closed (briefly $NC\alpha^{**}$ -closed) iff for each $\mathcal{L}$ $NC\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{J}$, then $\psi(\mathcal{L})$ is a NC -CS in $\mathcal{J}$.

Definition 3.2: A function $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ is called:

i. Neutrosophic crisp semi- α -closed (briefly $NCS\alpha$ -closed) iff for each $\mathcal{L}$ NC -CS in $\mathcal{J}$, then $\psi(\mathcal{L})$ is a $NCS\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{J}$.

ii. Neutrosophic crisp semi- α^* -closed (briefly $NCS\alpha^*$ -closed) iff for each $\mathcal{L}$ $NCS\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{J}$, then $\psi(\mathcal{L})$ is a $NCS\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{J}$.

iii. Neutrosophic crisp semi- α^{**} -closed (briefly $NCS\alpha^{**}$ -closed) iff for each $\mathcal{L}$ $NCS\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{J}$, then $\psi(\mathcal{L})$ is a NC -CS in $\mathcal{J}$.

Theorem 3.3: A function $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ is $NCS\alpha$ -closed iff for every $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{J}$, $NC-int(NC-cl(NC-int(NC-cl(\psi(\mathcal{L})))) \subseteq \psi(NC-cl(\mathcal{L}))$.

Proof:

Necessity: For any $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{J}$, $\psi(NC-cl(\mathcal{L}))$ is $NCS\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{J}$ this implies that

$$NC-int(NC-cl(NC-int(\psi(NC-cl(\mathcal{L})))) \subseteq \psi(NC-cl(\mathcal{L})).$$

Hence, we have

$$NC-int(NC-cl(NC-int(NC-cl(\psi(\mathcal{L})))) \subseteq \psi(NC-cl(\mathcal{L})).$$

Sufficiency: For any $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{J}$, we have by hypothesis

$$NC-int(NC-cl(NC-int(NC-cl(\psi(\mathcal{L})))) \subseteq \psi(NC-cl(\mathcal{L})).$$

So $\psi(\mathcal{L})$ is $NCS\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{J}$ and then we get that the function ψ is a $NCS\alpha$ -closed. ■

Theorem 3.4:

i. Any function NC -closed is $NC\alpha$ -closed, then it is $NCS\alpha$ -closed. Nonetheless, the inverse is generally a fallacy.

ii. Any function $NC\alpha$ -closed is $NCS\alpha$ -closed. Nonetheless, the inverse is generally a fallacy.

Proof:

i. Assume $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ is a NC -closed function, and $\mathcal{L}$ is a NC -CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Then $\psi(\mathcal{L})$ is a NC -CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Because NC -CS is $NC\alpha$ -CS ($NCS\alpha$ -CS), $\psi(\mathcal{L})$ is a $NC\alpha$ -CS ($NCS\alpha$ -CS) in $\mathcal{J}$. Thus, the function ψ is $NC\alpha$ -closed ($NCS\alpha$ -closed).

ii. Assume $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ is a $NC\alpha$ -closed function and $\mathcal{L}$ is a NC -CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Then $\psi(\mathcal{L})$ is a $NC\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Because $NC\alpha$ -CS is $NCS\alpha$ -CS, $\psi(\mathcal{L})$ is a $NCS\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Thus, the function ψ is $NCS\alpha$ -closed. ■

Example 3.5: Assume $\mathcal{J} = \{p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4\}$. Then

$$\zeta_{\mathcal{J}} = \{\phi_N, \langle \{p_3\}, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle \{p_1, p_3\}, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle \{p_1, p_2, p_3\}, \phi, \phi \rangle, \mathcal{J}_N\}$$

is a NCTS. The collection of every NC -CSs of $\mathcal{J}$ is:

$$NC-C(\mathcal{J}) = \{\mathcal{J}_N, \langle \{p_1, p_2, p_4\}, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle \{p_2, p_4\}, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle \{p_4\}, \phi, \phi \rangle, \phi_N\}.$$

The collection of every $NC\alpha$ -CSs ($NCS\alpha$ -CSs) of $\mathcal{J}$ is:

$$NCS\alpha C(\mathcal{J}) = NC\alpha C(\mathcal{J}) = NC-C(\mathcal{J}) \cup \{\langle \{p_1, p_4\}, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle \{p_1, p_2\}, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle \{p_2\}, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle \{p_1\}, \phi, \phi \rangle\}.$$

Define a function $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ by

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(\langle \{p_1\}, \phi, \phi \rangle) &= \langle \{p_1\}, \phi, \phi \rangle, \psi(\langle \{p_2\}, \phi, \phi \rangle) = \langle \{p_4\}, \phi, \phi \rangle, \\ \psi(\langle \{p_3\}, \phi, \phi \rangle) &= \langle \{p_3\}, \phi, \phi \rangle, \psi(\langle \{p_4\}, \phi, \phi \rangle) = \langle \{p_2\}, \phi, \phi \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

We observe ψ is a $NC\alpha$ -closed. It is $NCS\alpha$ -closed; nonetheless, it is not a NC -closed function because of $\langle \{p_4\}, \phi, \phi \rangle$ is NC -CS in $\mathcal{J}$ and $\psi(\langle \{p_4\}, \phi, \phi \rangle) = \langle \{p_2\}, \phi, \phi \rangle$ is not a NC -CS in $\mathcal{J}$.

Example 3.6: Let $\mathcal{J} = \{p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4\}$. Then

$$\zeta_{\mathcal{J}} = \{\phi_N, \langle\{p_1\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_2\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_1, p_2\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_1, p_2, p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \mathcal{J}_N\}$$

is a NCTS. The collection of every NC-CSs of $\mathcal{J}$ is:

$$\text{NC-C}(\mathcal{J}) = \{\mathcal{J}_N, \langle\{p_2, p_3, p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_1, p_3, p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_3, p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \phi_N\}.$$

The collection of every NC α -CSs of $\mathcal{J}$ is:

$$\text{NC}\alpha\text{C}(\mathcal{J}) = \text{NC-C}(\mathcal{J}) \cup \{\langle\{p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle\}.$$

The collection of every NCS α -CSs of $\mathcal{J}$ is:

$$\text{NCS}\alpha\text{C}(\mathcal{J}) = \text{NC}\alpha\text{C}(\mathcal{J}) \cup \{\langle\{p_2, p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_2, p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_1, p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_1, p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_2\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_1\}, \phi, \phi\rangle\}.$$

Define a function $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ by

$$\psi(\langle\{p_1\}, \phi, \phi\rangle) = \langle\{p_1\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \psi(\langle\{p_2\}, \phi, \phi\rangle) = \langle\{p_2\}, \phi, \phi\rangle,$$

$$\psi(\langle\{p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle) = \psi(\langle\{p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle) = \langle\{p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle.$$

We observe that the function ψ is a NCS α -closed. Furthermore, it is not NC α -closed function because of $\langle\{p_1, p_3, p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle$ is NC-CS in $\mathcal{J}$ and $\psi(\langle\{p_1, p_3, p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle) = \langle\{p_1, p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle$ is not a NC α -CS in $\mathcal{J}$.

Remark 3.7: There is no relation between the ideas of NC-closed and NC α^* -closed functions, as the next two examples are displayed below.

Example 3.8: The function ψ in Example (3.5) is a NC α^* -closed. Nonetheless, it is not NC-closed.

Example 3.9: Assume that $\mathcal{J} = \{p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4\}$ is a set. Then

$$\zeta_{\mathcal{J}} = \{\phi_N, \langle\{p_1\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_2\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_1, p_2\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_1, p_2, p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \mathcal{J}_N\}$$

is a NCTS. The collection of each NC-CSs of $\mathcal{J}$ is:

$$\text{NC-C}(\mathcal{J}) = \{\mathcal{J}_N, \langle\{p_2, p_3, p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_1, p_3, p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_3, p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \phi_N\}.$$

The family of all NC α -CSs of $\mathcal{J}$ is: $\text{NC}\alpha\text{C}(\mathcal{J}) = \text{NC-C}(\mathcal{J}) \cup \{\langle\{p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle\}$. The collection of each NCS α -CSs of $\mathcal{J}$ is:

$$\text{NCS}\alpha\text{C}(\mathcal{J}) = \text{NC}\alpha\text{C}(\mathcal{J}) \cup \{\langle\{p_2, p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_2, p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_1, p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_1, p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_2\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_1\}, \phi, \phi\rangle\}$$

Define a function $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ by

$$\psi(\langle\{p_1\}, \phi, \phi\rangle) = \psi(\langle\{p_2\}, \phi, \phi\rangle) = \langle\{p_1\}, \phi, \phi\rangle,$$

$$\psi(\langle\{p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle) = \langle\{p_2\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \psi(\langle\{p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle) = \langle\{p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle.$$

We observe that the ψ is a NC-closed. Furthermore, it is not NC α^* -closed function because of $\langle\{p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle$ is NC α -CS in $\mathcal{J}$ and $\psi(\langle\{p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle) = \langle\{p_2\}, \phi, \phi\rangle$ is not a NC α -CS in $\mathcal{J}$.

Proposition 3.10:

- i. A function $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ is NC-closed and NC-continuous, then this function is NC α^* -closed.
- ii. A function $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ is a NC α^* -closed iff $\psi: (\mathcal{J}, \text{NC}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{J})) \rightarrow (\mathcal{J}, \text{NC}\alpha\text{O}(\mathcal{J}))$ is NC-closed.

Proof:

- i. Assume that a function $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ is NC-closed and NC-continuous. To verify the function ψ is NC α^* -closed, we suppose that $\mathcal{L} \in \text{NC}\alpha\text{C}(\mathcal{J})$, then for some sets like NC-CS $\mathcal{N}$ with this fact $\text{NC-cl}(\text{NC-int}(\mathcal{N})) \subseteq \mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{N}$ (by theorem (2.4)). Hence $\psi(\text{NC-cl}(\text{NC-int}(\mathcal{N}))) \subseteq \psi(\mathcal{L}) \subseteq \psi(\mathcal{N})$ but $\text{NC-cl}(\psi(\text{NC-int}(\mathcal{N}))) \subseteq \psi(\text{NC-cl}(\text{NC-int}(\mathcal{N})))$ (because the function ψ is NC-closed). Then $\text{NC-cl}(\psi(\text{NC-int}(\mathcal{N}))) \subseteq \psi(\text{NC-cl}(\text{NC-int}(\mathcal{N}))) \subseteq \psi(\mathcal{L}) \subseteq \psi(\mathcal{N})$. But $\text{NC-cl}(\text{NC-int}(\psi(\mathcal{N}))) \subseteq \text{NC-cl}(\psi(\text{NC-int}(\mathcal{N})))$ (because the function ψ is NC-continuous). Consequently, we get $\text{NC-cl}(\text{NC-int}(\psi(\mathcal{N}))) \subseteq \psi(\mathcal{L}) \subseteq \psi(\mathcal{N})$. However, $\psi(\mathcal{N})$ is a NC-CS in $\mathcal{J}$ (because the function ψ is NC-closed). Hence $\psi(\mathcal{L}) \in \text{NC}\alpha\text{C}(\mathcal{J})$ (it is clear from theorem (2.4)). Thus, the function ψ is NC α^* -closed.

ii. Part (ii) is clear for proof. ■

Remark 3.11: It is understood that every function is defined as $NC\alpha^*$ -closed, then it is $NC\alpha$ -closed as well as $NCS\alpha$ -closed. Nonetheless, the inverse is generally a fallacy, as the next example is displayed below.

Example 3.12: It is clear to note that the function ψ is a $NC\alpha$ -closed and $NCS\alpha$ -closed in Example (3.12). However, it is not $NC\alpha^*$ -closed.

Remark 3.13: There is no relation between the ideas of NC-closed and $NCS\alpha^*$ -closed functions, as the next two examples are displayed below.

Example 3.14: The function ψ in Example (3.5) is a $NCS\alpha^*$ -closed. However, it is not NC-closed.

Example 3.15: Let $\mathcal{J} = \{p_1, p_2, p_3\}$. Then $\zeta = \{\phi_N, \langle\{p_1\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \mathcal{J}_N\}$ is a NCTS. The collection of each NC-CSs of $\mathcal{J}$ is $NC-C(\mathcal{J}) = \{\mathcal{J}_N, \langle\{p_2, p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \phi_N\}$. The collection of each $NC\alpha$ -CSs ($NCS\alpha$ -CSs) of $\mathcal{J}$ is:

$$NC\alpha C(\mathcal{J}) = NCS\alpha C(\mathcal{J}) = NC-C(\mathcal{J}) \cup \{\langle\{p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_2\}, \phi, \phi\rangle\}.$$

Let $\mathcal{J} = \{q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4\}$. Then $\eta = \{\phi_N, \langle\{q_1\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{q_2, q_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{q_1, q_2, q_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \mathcal{J}_N\}$ is a NCTS.

The collection of each NC-CSs of $\mathcal{J}$ is:

$$NC-C(\mathcal{J}) = \{\mathcal{J}_N, \langle\{q_2, q_3, q_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{q_1, q_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{q_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \phi_N\}.$$

The collection of each $NC\alpha$ -CSs of $\mathcal{J}$ is: $NC\alpha C(\mathcal{J}) = NC-C(\mathcal{J})$. The family of all $NCS\alpha$ -CSs of $\mathcal{J}$ is:

$$NCS\alpha C(\mathcal{J}) = NC\alpha C(\mathcal{J}) \cup \{\langle\{q_1\}, \phi, \phi\rangle\}.$$

Define a function $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ by

$$\psi(\langle\{p_1\}, \phi, \phi\rangle) = \langle\{q_1\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \psi(\langle\{p_2\}, \phi, \phi\rangle) = \langle\{q_2\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \psi(\langle\{p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle) = \langle\{q_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle.$$

Clearly, we can realize that the function ψ is a NC-closed; nonetheless, this function doesn't represent $NCS\alpha^*$ -closed because of $\langle\{p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle \in NCS\alpha C(\mathcal{J})$ and $\psi(\langle\{p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle) = \langle\{q_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle \notin NCS\alpha C(\mathcal{J})$.

Proposition 3.16: A function $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ is a $NCS\alpha^*$ -closed iff this function $\psi: (\mathcal{J}, NCS\alpha O(\mathcal{J})) \rightarrow (\mathcal{J}, NCS\alpha O(\mathcal{J}))$ is a NC-closed.

Proof: Understandable. ■

Remark 3.17: There is no relation between the ideas of $NC\alpha^*$ -closed and $NCS\alpha^*$ -closed functions, as the next two examples are displayed below.

Example 3.18: The function ψ in Example (3.9) is a $NCS\alpha^*$ -closed. However, it is not $NC\alpha^*$ -closed.

Example 3.19: Assume that the set $\mathcal{J} = \{p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4\}$. Then

$$\zeta = \{\phi_N, \langle\{p_1\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_2, p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_1, p_2, p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \mathcal{J}_N\}$$

is a NCTS. The collection of each NC-CSs of $\mathcal{J}$ is:

$$NC-C(\mathcal{J}) = \{\mathcal{J}_N, \langle\{p_2, p_3, p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_1, p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \phi_N\}.$$

Assume that the set $\mathcal{J} = \{q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4\}$. Then

$$\eta = \{\phi_N, \langle\{q_1\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{q_2, q_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{q_1, q_2, q_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \mathcal{J}_N\}$$

is a NCTS. The collection of each NC-CSs of $\mathcal{J}$ is

$$NC-C(\mathcal{J}) = \{\mathcal{J}_N, \langle\{q_2, q_3, q_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{q_1, q_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \langle\{q_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \phi_N\}.$$

Define a function $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ by

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(\langle\{p_1\}, \phi, \phi\rangle) &= \langle\{q_1\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \\ \psi(\langle\{p_2\}, \phi, \phi\rangle) &= \psi(\langle\{p_3\}, \phi, \phi\rangle) = \langle\{q_2\}, \phi, \phi\rangle, \\ \psi(\langle\{p_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle) &= \langle\{q_4\}, \phi, \phi\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Clearly, we can note that the function ψ is $NC\alpha^*$ -closed. However, it is not $NCS\alpha^*$ -closed.

Theorem 3.20: If a function $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ is $\text{NC}\alpha^*$ -closed and NC-continuous, then it is $\text{NCS}\alpha^*$ -closed.

Proof: Assume that the function $\psi: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ is $\text{NC}\alpha^*$ -closed as well as NC-continuous. Moreover, suppose $\mathcal{L}$ is $\text{NCS}\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Then for some sets, like $\text{NC}\alpha$ -CS $\mathcal{N}$ with this fact $\text{NC-int}(\mathcal{N}) \subseteq \mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{N}$. Consequently, we have

$$\text{NC-int}(\psi(\mathcal{N})) \subseteq \psi(\text{NC-int}(\mathcal{N})) \subseteq \psi(\mathcal{L}) \subseteq \psi(\mathcal{N})$$

(this is because the function ψ is NC-continuous). However, the set $\psi(\mathcal{N}) \in \text{NC}\alpha\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J})$ because the function ψ is $\text{NC}\alpha^*$ -closed). Thus, the set $\text{NC-int}(\psi(\mathcal{N})) \subseteq \psi(\mathcal{L}) \subseteq \psi(\mathcal{N})$. Therefore, $\psi(\mathcal{L}) \in \text{NCS}\alpha\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J})$. Thus, ψ is a $\text{NCS}\alpha^*$ -closed function. ■

Theorem 3.21: The two functions $\psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ and $\psi_2: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ are satisfying the following

- i. If a function ψ_1 is NC-closed and a function ψ_2 is $\text{NC}\alpha$ -closed, then a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is $\text{NC}\alpha$ -closed.
- ii. If a function ψ_1 is $\text{NC}\alpha$ -closed and a function ψ_2 is $\text{NC}\alpha^*$ -closed, then a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is $\text{NC}\alpha$ -closed.
- iii. If functions ψ_1 and ψ_2 are $\text{NC}\alpha^*$ -closed, then a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is $\text{NC}\alpha^*$ -closed.
- iv. If functions ψ_1 and ψ_2 are $\text{NCS}\alpha^*$ -closed, then a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is $\text{NCS}\alpha^*$ -closed.
- v. If functions ψ_1 and ψ_2 are $\text{NC}\alpha^{**}$ -closed, then a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is $\text{NC}\alpha^{**}$ -closed.
- vi. If functions ψ_1 and ψ_2 are $\text{NCS}\alpha^{**}$ -closed, then a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is $\text{NCS}\alpha^{**}$ -closed.
- vii. If a function ψ_1 is $\text{NC}\alpha^{**}$ -closed and a function ψ_2 is $\text{NC}\alpha^*$ -closed, then a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is $\text{NC}\alpha^*$ -closed.
- viii. If a function ψ_1 is $\text{NC}\alpha$ -closed and a function ψ_2 is $\text{NC}\alpha^{**}$ -closed, then a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is NC-closed.
- ix. If a function ψ_1 is $\text{NC}\alpha^{**}$ -closed and a function ψ_2 is $\text{NC}\alpha$ -closed, then a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is $\text{NC}\alpha^*$ -closed.
- x. If a function ψ_1 is $\text{NC}\alpha^{**}$ -closed and a function ψ_2 is NC-closed, then a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is a $\text{NC}\alpha^{**}$ -closed.

Proof:

- i. Let $\mathcal{L}$ be a NC-CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_1 is a NC-closed function, $\psi_1(\mathcal{L})$ is a NC-CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_2 is a $\text{NC}\alpha$ -closed function, $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1(\mathcal{L}) = \psi_2(\psi_1(\mathcal{L}))$ is a $\text{NC}\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{K}$. Thus, a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is $\text{NC}\alpha$ -closed.
- ii. Let $\mathcal{L}$ be a NC-CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_1 is a $\text{NC}\alpha$ -closed function, $\psi_1(\mathcal{L})$ is a $\text{NC}\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_2 is a $\text{NC}\alpha^*$ -closed function, $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1(\mathcal{L}) = \psi_2(\psi_1(\mathcal{L}))$ is a $\text{NC}\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{K}$. Thus, a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is $\text{NC}\alpha$ -closed.
- iii. Let $\mathcal{L}$ be a $\text{NC}\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_1 is a $\text{NC}\alpha^*$ -closed function, $\psi_1(\mathcal{L})$ is a $\text{NC}\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_2 is a $\text{NC}\alpha^*$ -closed function, $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1(\mathcal{L}) = \psi_2(\psi_1(\mathcal{L}))$ is a $\text{NC}\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{K}$. Thus, a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is $\text{NC}\alpha^*$ -closed.
- iv. Let $\mathcal{L}$ be a $\text{NCS}\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_1 is a $\text{NCS}\alpha^*$ -closed function, $\psi_1(\mathcal{L})$ is a $\text{NCS}\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_2 is a $\text{NCS}\alpha^*$ -closed function, $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1(\mathcal{L}) = \psi_2(\psi_1(\mathcal{L}))$ is a $\text{NCS}\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{K}$. Thus, a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is $\text{NCS}\alpha^*$ -closed.
- v. Let $\mathcal{L}$ be a $\text{NC}\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_1 is a $\text{NC}\alpha^{**}$ -closed function, $\psi_1(\mathcal{L})$ is a NC-CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Since any NC-CS is $\text{NC}\alpha$ -CS, $\psi_1(\mathcal{L})$ is a $\text{NC}\alpha$ -CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_2 is a $\text{NC}\alpha^{**}$ -closed function, $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1(\mathcal{L}) = \psi_2(\psi_1(\mathcal{L}))$ is a NC-CS in $\mathcal{K}$. Thus, a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is $\text{NC}\alpha^{**}$ -closed.

- vi. Let $\mathcal{L}$ be a $\text{NCS}\alpha\text{-CS}$ in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_1 is a $\text{NCS}\alpha^{**}\text{-closed}$ function, $\psi_1(\mathcal{L})$ is a NC-CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Since any NC-CS is $\text{NCS}\alpha\text{-CS}$, $\psi_1(\mathcal{L})$ is a $\text{NCS}\alpha\text{-CS}$ in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_2 is a $\text{NCS}\alpha^{**}\text{-closed}$ function, $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1(\mathcal{L}) = \psi_2(\psi_1(\mathcal{L}))$ is a NC-CS in $\mathcal{K}$. Thus, a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is $\text{NCS}\alpha^{**}\text{-closed}$.
- vii. Let $\mathcal{L}$ be a $\text{NC}\alpha\text{-CS}$ in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_1 is a $\text{NC}\alpha^{**}\text{-closed}$ function, $\psi_1(\mathcal{L})$ is a NC-CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Since any NC-CS is $\text{NC}\alpha\text{-CS}$, $\psi_1(\mathcal{L})$ is a $\text{NC}\alpha\text{-CS}$ in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_2 is a $\text{NC}\alpha^*\text{-closed}$ function, $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1(\mathcal{L}) = \psi_2(\psi_1(\mathcal{L}))$ is a $\text{NC}\alpha\text{-CS}$ in $\mathcal{K}$. Thus, a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is $\text{NC}\alpha^*\text{-closed}$.
- viii. Let $\mathcal{L}$ be a NC-CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_1 is a $\text{NC}\alpha\text{-closed}$ function, $\psi_1(\mathcal{L})$ is a $\text{NC}\alpha\text{-CS}$ in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_2 is a $\text{NC}\alpha^{**}\text{-closed}$ function, $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1(\mathcal{L}) = \psi_2(\psi_1(\mathcal{L}))$ is a NC-CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Thus, a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is NC-closed .
- ix. Let $\mathcal{L}$ be a $\text{NC}\alpha\text{-CS}$ in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_1 is a $\text{NC}\alpha^{**}\text{-closed}$ function, $\psi_1(\mathcal{L})$ is a NC-CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_2 is a $\text{NC}\alpha\text{-closed}$ function, $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1(\mathcal{L}) = \psi_2(\psi_1(\mathcal{L}))$ is a $\text{NC}\alpha\text{-CS}$ in $\mathcal{J}$. Thus, a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is a $\text{NC}\alpha^*\text{-closed}$.
- x. Let $\mathcal{L}$ be a $\text{NC}\alpha\text{-CS}$ in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_1 is a $\text{NC}\alpha^{**}\text{-closed}$ function, $\psi_1(\mathcal{L})$ is a NC-CS in $\mathcal{J}$. Since ψ_2 is a NC-closed function, $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1(\mathcal{L}) = \psi_2(\psi_1(\mathcal{L}))$ is a NC-CS in $\mathcal{L}$. Thus, a function $\psi_2 \circ \psi_1: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{K}$ is $\text{NC}\alpha^{**}\text{-closed}$. ■

Remark 3.22: The following diagram on the next page explains the relationship between weakly NC-closed functions.

Fig. 3.1

4. Conclusion

We utilize the ideas of $\text{NC}\alpha\text{-CS}$ s and $\text{NCS}\alpha\text{-CS}$ s to identify some different kinds of weakly NC-closed functions, for instance; $\text{NC}\alpha^*\text{-closed}$, $\text{NC}\alpha^{**}\text{-closed}$, $\text{NCS}\alpha\text{-closed}$, $\text{NCS}\alpha^*\text{-closed}$ and $\text{NCS}\alpha^{**}\text{-closed}$ functions. The most significant results are that the neutrosophic crisp semi- $\alpha^{**}\text{-closed}$ maps are neutrosophic crisp $\alpha^{**}\text{-closed}$, neutrosophic crisp $\alpha^*\text{-closed}$ and

neutrosophic crisp semi- α^* -closed. Moreover, neutrosophic crisp α^{**} -closed map is neutrosophic crisp α^* -closed and neutrosophic crisp closed. However, the neutrosophic crisp closed map is not neutrosophic crisp α^* -closed and the latter is not neutrosophic crisp semi- α^* -closed unless they are NC-continuous maps. Furthermore, neutrosophic crisp α^* -closed and neutrosophic crisp closed maps are neutrosophic crisp α -closed and neutrosophic crisp semi- α -closed because crisp α -closed map is neutrosophic crisp semi- α -closed. Finally, neutrosophic crisp semi- α^* -closed map is neutrosophic crisp semi- α -closed. As future works, the $NC\alpha$ -CSs and $NCS\alpha$ -CSs can be used to derive some neutrosophic crisp separation axioms, and we can generalize our results from the multivalued neutrosophic crisp closed.

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